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plant yield to 4 kg/plant, as compared to 2.2 kg/plant in the untreated control.

V5

MONITORING OF NEW EMERGING EGGPLANT VIRAL DISEASE IN JORDAN VALLEY. Abeer Abu Shirbi, National Center for Agricultural Research and Extension (NCARE), P.O. Box 639 Baqa 19381, Jordan, Email: abeer@ncare.gov.jo

Over the last two decades, intensive agriculture has been developed rapidly in the Jordan Valley. Some viruses were recorded for the first time in Jordan. Early detection and identification of newly emerging viruses is critical for implementation of proper control methods. The aim of this study was to do identify and characterize the causal agent of a newly viral disease of eggplant (*Solanum melongena*) in Jordan. The virus disease was first observed in the field during 2012. The disease was transmitted mechanically from infected source plants to healthy eggplant. It has different host range. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) of purified virus preparations indicated the presence of flexible filamentous particles (approximately 720 nm long). Moreover, TEM of ultrathin sections of infected tissue revealed the presence of pinwheel cytoplasmic inclusion bodies and crystalline structures, typical of potyviral infection. The *Tomato mild mottle Ipomovirus* (TomMMoV) was identified by RT-PCR with two sets of primers (amplicon sizes 1200 bp and 700 bp). The viral particles reacted positively in ELISA using antisera against TomMMoV. The virus was transmitted by the aphid vector *Myzus persicae*. The current study also revealed some biological properties of *Eggplant mild leaf mottle Ipomovirus* (EMLMV), which is transmitted by the whitefly *Bemisia tabaci*, but not by three aphid species.

V6

EVALUATION OF TWO APPLICATION METHODS OF FOUR STRAINS OF PLANT GROWTH PROMOTING RHIZOBACTER TO INDUCE SYSTEMIC RESISTANCE AGAINST CUCUMBER MOSAIC VIRUS IN TOMATO PLANTS IN THE GREENHOUSE. Hanan Qawas¹, Omar Hamoudi², Ahmed Ahmed³ and Emad Daoud Ismail¹. (1) Department of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Tishreen University, Lattakia, Syria, Email: Hanankawas1@gmail.com; (2) Agricultural Research Center, Lattakia, Syria; (3) Agricultural Research Center, Tartous, Syria.

The study was conducted to evaluate two application methods of four strains of plant growth promoting rhizobacter: *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* MA342, *Serratia plymuthica* HRO-C48, *Bacillus subtilis* B2g, and *B. subtilis* FZB27 to induce systemic resistance in tomato plants against *cucumber mosaic virus* (CMV) under greenhouse conditions. In the “treated seed” application, tomato seeds were submerged in a suspension of *Pseudomonas chlororaphis* MA342, *Serratia plymuthica* HRO-C48, *Bacillus subtilis* B2g or *B. subtilis* FZB27 (10^{10} cfu/ml), and in “treated seed + irrigation” application, seeds were treated in the same way, 10 days after transplanting, every transplant was irrigated with 10 ml of each suspension (10^9 /ml), and 19 days after transplanting were

inoculated with CMV. The time required for initial symptoms development was recorded. In addition, disease incidence, disease severity and peroxidase enzyme activity were also determined. Results of this study showed that treatment with the four strains delayed the time of symptoms appearance compared with the infected control. The delay was more in the “treated seed + irrigation” application than in the “treated seed” application. The treatment with four bacterial strains decreased disease incidence in treated plants which ranged between 36.11%-46.65% and 45%-63.33% 14 and 30 days after inoculation, respectively. Consequently, the highest reduction in infection rate was with the strain B27 (treated seed + irrigation). The treatment with bacterial strains reduced infection severity 14 and 30 days after inoculation, and the reduction was higher in the “treated seed + irrigation” application than in the “treated seed” for all the evaluated bacterial strains. The B27 strain with “treated seed + irrigation” application gave the best effect compared with the other three strains, with reduction in infection rate of 57.14% and 60.36%, 14 and 30 days after inoculation, respectively. The treatment with bacteria improved the peroxidase enzyme activity in the inoculated treated plants with recorded activity of 0.039- 0.097 n mol and 0.106-0.271 n mol compared with the infected control (0.021 n mol) and the healthy control (0.022 n mol) 14 and 30 days after inoculation, respectively. The B27 strain in the “treated seed + irrigation” application gave the best result.

V7

SURVEY OF THE SANITARY STATUS OF ANCIENT NATIVE GRAPEVINE CULTIVARS FROM APULIA (ITALY) BY REALTIME-RT-PCR. Raied Abou Kubaa¹, Massimiliano Morelli¹, Angelantonio Minafra¹, Giovanna Bottalico², Antonietta Campanale¹ and Pasquale Saldarelli¹. (1) Istituto di Virologia Vegetale del CNR, UOS Bari, Via Amendola 165/A, 70126, Bari, Italy, Email: raied.aboukubaa@ipsp.cnr.it; (2) Dipartimento di Scienze del Suolo, della Pianta e degli Alimenti (Di. S. S. P. A.), Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro, 70126 Bari, Italy.

A study of the sanitary status of ancient native grapevine cultivars and biotypes of Apulia (Italy) was performed in the framework of the project Re. Ge. Vi. P. (“Recovery of Apulian grape germplasm”). A total of 80 native table and wine grapes (the majority of which described in historical pre-philloxera reports) were recovered throughout the Apulian territory and their dormant canes used for virus screening by ELISA for the presence of *Grapevine virus A* (GVA), *Grapevine virus B* (GVB), *Grapevine leafroll-associated virus-1*, -2 and -3 (GLRaV-1, -2 and -3), *Grapevine fanleaf virus* (GFLV), *Grapevine fleck virus* (GFkV) and *Arabidopsis mosaic virus* (ArMV), using commercial kits (Agritest s. r. l., Italy). Certified plant propagation material of grapevine should be free of these viruses according to the Italian Law. Selected accessions were propagated and those positive for single or multiple virus infections were submitted to sanitation. Overall, at least three plantlets deriving from distinct apex excisions (totally 242) were transferred to the greenhouse after acclimatization and were tested after 60 days by

REALTIME-RT-PCR for all the viruses above indicated, in 242 apexes tested, that GFLV and GFKV were the most frequently detected viruses showing 9.5% and 8.2% infection rate, respectively, followed by GVA (4.9%), GLRaV3 (2.9%) and GVB (1.6%). Furthermore, all plants reacted negatively to GLRaV-1, GLRaV-2 as well as ArMV which is known to be rare in the Mediterranean area, mainly because of the low occurrence of its vector, *Xyphinema diversicaudatum*. Mixed infections by more than one virus were found in some plants assuming the failure of sanitation procedure to eliminate these viruses. The persistence of infection by GVA, GVB, GLRaV3 and GFKV in some apexes, which was not detected by the preliminary ELISA screening of source plants, underlines the higher sensitivity of Realtime-RT-PCR in detecting these viruses

V8
DISTRIBUTION AND MANAGEMENT OF BEET WESTERN YELLOWS AND CHICKPEA CHLOROTIC STUNT VIRUSES IN TUNISIA. Samia Mghandef^{1,2}, Safaa G. Kumari², Joop van Leur³ and Asma Najar⁴. (1) Faculté des Sciences de Bizerte, Bizerte, Tunisia, Email: mghandefsamia91@gmail.com; (2) International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas, Terbol Station, Zahla, Lebanon, Email: s.kumari@cgiar.org; (3) NSW Department of Primary Industries, Tamworth Agricultural Institute, New South Wales, Australia, Email: joop.vanleur@dpi.nsw.gov.au; (4) National Agricultural Research Institute of Tunisia (INRAT), Ariana, Tunisia, Email: asmanajara@yahoo.fr

A field survey to determine the extent of the spread of *Beet western yellows virus* (BWYV) and *Chickpea chlorotic stunt virus* (CpCSV) (genus *Polerovirus*, family *Luteoviridae*) on faba bean and chickpea in five main regions in Tunisia (Béja, Bizerte, Cap Bon, Jendouba and Kef) was conducted during 2014/2015 growing season. A total of 599 faba bean and 843 chickpea samples with yellowing, reddening and/or stunting symptoms were collected from 49 faba bean and 48 chickpea fields. Tissue blot immunoassay (TBIA) test detected BWYV and CpCSV in all surveyed regions. Around 45% of chickpea and 8% faba bean samples tested were infected with CpCSV, whereas BWYV was only detected in 12% of faba bean and 7% of chickpea samples. The usefulness of seed-dressing with two pesticides to reduce spread of the aphid vectored BWYV and CpCSV was investigated in a field experiment, using artificial virus inoculation. Seeds of three Tunisian chickpea cultivars (Beja 1, Chetoui and Bouchra) were treated with Celest top (25g/L difenoconazole + 25 g/L fludioxonil + 262.5 g/L thiamethoxam) at the rate of 0.7, 1.5 and 3.0 cc/kg of seeds and with Apron Star 45 WS (200 g/kg thiamethoxam, 200 g/kg mefenoxam, 20 g/kg difenoconazole) at the rate of 1.25, 2.5 and 5.0 g/kg compared with untreated seeds (control). Seven weeks after sowing, all plants were artificially inoculated with BWYV and CpCSV using viruliferous *Myzus persicae* (Sulzer) and *Aphis craccivora* Koch, respectively. Results obtained showed that the spread of BWYV and CpCSV and yield loss caused by them were significantly reduced in treated plots compared with untreated plots. Around 182 chickpea and 72 lentil

germplasm accessions from ICARDA's Gene Bank were selected to represent a wide range of geographical origins were evaluated for their reaction to local Tunisian isolates of BWYV and CpCSV under field conditions during 2015/2016 growing season. Resistance screening for each virus was done in separate field trials. All tested plants were inoculated with BWYV and CpCSV using viruliferous *M. persicae* and *A. craccivora*, respectively. Reaction of the different genotypes to virus infection were monitored by evaluating (i) disease severity (DS) (score 0-3), (ii) virus existing and distribution (using TBIA test), and (iii) yield. Few lentil genotypes were found tolerant to CpCSV (IG 343) and BWYV (IG 5384); and few chickpea genotypes were tolerant to CpCSV (IG 69719) and BWYV (IG 9406).

V9
PRELIMINARY SCREENING OF FABA BEAN GENOTYPES FOR RESISTANCE TO BEET WESTERN YELLOWS VIRUS. Safaa G. Kumari^{1,2}, Joop van Leur³, Marwa Ben Omrane² and Samia Mghandef². (1) International Center for Agricultural Research in the Dry Areas (ICARDA), Terbol Station, Beqa'a Valley, Zahla, Lebanon, Email: s.kumari@cgiar.org; (2) ICARDA, Tunis, Tunisia; (3) NSW Department of Primary Industries, Tamworth Agricultural Institute, New South Wales, Australia, Email: joop.vanleur@dpi.nsw.gov.au

Beet western yellows virus (BWYV, genus *Polerovirus*, family *Luteoviridae*) causes a serious disease to several crop and weed species, especially these belonging to *Brassicaceae*, *Compositae* and *Fabaceae* families. The main symptoms in response to BWYV infection are leaf yellowing, plant stunting, reddening and thickening of the leaves and reduction in pod setting of legume crops. BWYV is persistently transmitted by aphids only, mainly *Myzus persicae*. BWYV have been reported in many countries of Central and West Asia and North Africa (CWANA) region. Host resistance is the most acceptable component to control viral diseases because it is environment friendly, practical, and economically acceptable to farmers. In this study, populations of 27 single faba bean plants selected from the previous seasons with a high yield and tolerance to *Faba bean necrotic yellows virus* (FBNYV, genus *Nanovirus*, family *Nanoviridae*) infection (Syrian and Tunisian isolates), and registered at ICARDA's GeneBank under accession numbers from IG159162 to IG159188, were evaluated during the 2015/2016 and 2016/2017 growing seasons for their reaction to a local Tunisian isolate of BWYV under bee-proof greenhouse at Mornag station, Tunisia. All evaluated plants (15 plants/accession) were artificially inoculated with the BWYV using viruliferous *Myzus persicae* (10-15 aphids per plant). Reaction of the different accessions to virus infection was monitored by evaluating (i) incidence and severity of infection, (ii) virus distribution and concentration (using TBIA test), and (iii) plant yield. Plants characterized by mild or no symptoms, no or little virus content and good yield were identified during the 1st growing season (2015/2016). The selected best performing individual plants (40 plants represented 22 accessions) were harvested and re-evaluated during the 2nd growing season (2016/2017) using the same virus inoculation methodology.